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Abstract

Liquid Landscapes and Ephemeral Site-Specific Art and Architecture in the Era of Social Networks

Ephemeral art and architecture have a way of leaving permanent registers in social networks. They become footprints of past events, in constant change and growth as their dissemination expands through sharing, comments, likes, and hashtags. These digital traces become new elements of meaning within tourist scenography and contribute to constructing the cultural identity of a territory. Social media platforms alter the perception of such ephemeral interventions and redefine how territory is experienced, especially within the liquid dynamics of contemporary tourism. The solid, physical and tangible territory becomes a liquid landscape, reinterpreted in real-time by the digital nomad who inhabits it, challenging traditional criteria of territorial identity.

This conceptual framework is anchored in Bauman's theory of liquid modernity and its extensions into architecture and art. As previously observed in creative neighborhoods and temporary interventions, ephemeral actions increasingly function as cultural activators and tools for urban identity and social cohesion (De Souza, 2024). Furthermore, the redevelopment of obsolete industrial areas through artistic and educational

strategies, shows how site-specific creative practices are intertwined with sustainable urban transformation (De Souza & Naranjo, 2023).

Finally, this research acknowledges the influence of vertical and transversal educational methodologies, such as the integrated urban drawing and planning studios that encourage critical spatial analysis and interdisciplinary experimentation. These academic frameworks—rooted in experiential learning and collective authorship—shape new ways to design and document ephemeral architecture (De Souza, Ferrer, & Naranjo, 2023).

Keywords: *Ephemeral Architecture, Liquid Landscapes, social media, Territorial Identity, Creative Transformation, Experiential Learning*

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Curriculum vitae

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PhD. Architect with International Mention; Master in Analysis, Theory and History of Architecture, and Graduate in Fine Arts. Professor in the area of Composition, Projects, and Urban Planning at the School of Architecture, Universidad Europea de Canarias.

His thesis ‘The Fold in Architecture’ is a historical, critical, conceptual and experimental study of the application of Origami patterns in Architecture. With more than 15 years of international teaching experience, He is a member of three Research Groups and have participated in three R+D+I projects: 1 international and 2 nationals.

His three main research lines are: 1) Architecture and Design with Origami and Structural Folds, 2) Educational Innovation in Architecture, and 3) Sustainable Urbanism and Cultural Development, where he explores how art and culture can be drivers for urban development. Since 2000 he has worked professionally in the realization of architectural, art and interior design projects, stage art direction and graphic design.

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PhD. in Urbanism from UPC and PhD. in Geography from Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne; Master in Landscape Studies from ENSA Paris-La Villette; and Architect from ULPGC.

She is currently a professor at the School of Architecture, Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, teaching Urban Planning and landscape architecture. With over two decades of international experience in architecture, urbanism, and landscape, she has held positions in France as State Architect-Urbanist for the Ministry of Culture and as lecturer in various french academic institutions.

Her research focuses on heritage urbanism, sustainable territorial planning and the intersection of aesthetics, environment and culture in spatial development. She is a member of the URBSCAPES- TIDES research group and has contributed to international congresses and peer-reviewed publications on educational innovation, cultural heritage, and landscape integration. Her professional work combines urban design, territorial diagnostics, and landscape architecture with a strong emphasis on sustainability and cultural value.

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ERUA's WP5, "Achieving Social Change in ERUA's Local Communities and Regions"

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